

Polarographic Studies of Mixed Ligand Complexes Cadmium-Imidazole-Tartrate System

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The mixed ligand complexes of imidazole (Im) and tartrate (Tart) with Cd(II) have been studied polarographically at constant ionic strength, $\mu=2.0$ (NaNO₃). The reduction of the complexes at d.m.e. is reversible and diffusion-controlled. Four mixed complexes viz., [Cd(Im)(Tart)]; [Cd(Im)(Tart)₂]²⁻; [Cd(Im)₂(Tart)₂]²⁻ and [Cd(Im)₃(Tart)] are formed. Their overall stability constants at 25° are $\log \beta_{11}=4.52$, $\log \beta_{12}=4.4$, $\log \beta_{22}=6.0$ and $\log \beta_{31}=6.0$ respectively.

Li *et al* have studied polarographically the composition and stability constants of simple complexes of Cd(II) with imidazole in aqueous and alcoholic media. The composition and the stability constants were determined by Lingane's² method. Although the plot of $E_{1/2}$ vs $\log [\text{Im}]$ was a curve, it was interpreted³ as a composite of three straight lines. The analysis of these straight lines revealed the formation of three complexes, viz., [Cd(Im)₂]²⁺, [Cd(Im)₃]²⁺ and [Cd(Im)₄]²⁺ with stability constants, $\log \beta_2=5.07$, $\log \beta_3=6.46$ and $\log \beta_4=7.48$. Li *et al* also established that the site of binding on the imidazole molecule is the "pyridine" nitrogen rather than the "pyrrole" nitrogen. This shows that imidazole acts as a monodentate ligand. This conclusion is also borne out by the polarographic studies of the composition and stability constants of Cd(II)-pyrazole system by Crow⁴ who has reported the formation of four successive complexes. It may be pointed out that imidazole and pyrazole are isomeric compounds (the former is 1, 3-diazol glyoxaline while the latter is 1, 2-diazol glyoxaline). Since the maximum co-ordination number of Cd(II) is six, the formation of four successive complexes of Cd(II) with pyrazole clearly shows that pyrazole must be a monodentate ligand. It is well known that the method of DeFord and Hume⁵ is applied for determining the overall stability constants of consecutively formed metal-ligand complexes undergoing reversible reduction at d.m.e. However, the method employed by Li *et al* for studying the composition and the stability constants of the consecutive complexes of Cd(II) with imidazole was not accurate⁶. It was, therefore, thought worthwhile to undertake the polarographic study of the simple complexes of Cd(II) with imidazole and also the mixed complexes of Cd(II) with imidazole and tartrate ions. This has not been done so far.

Experimental

Materials and Methods: All the reagents used were of analytical grade and their solutions were prepared in conductivity water. The ionic strength

was maintained constant at 2.0M using NaNO₃ as supporting electrolyte. Imidazole and sodium-potassium-tartrate were used as ligands. The concentration of Cd(II) was kept at $1 \times 10^{-3}M$. Polarograms were obtained by means of a manual polarograph (Toshniwal CLO2) in conjunction with Toshniwal polyflex galvanometer (PL 50). Purified nitrogen was used for removing the dissolved oxygen. All the measurements were made at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$. Saturated calomel electrode (S.C.E.) was used as reference electrode. The d.m.e. had the following characteristics (in 0.1M NaNO₃, open circuit): $m=1.498$ mg/sec, $t=2.75$ sec, $m^{2/3}t^{1/6}=1.5496$ mg^{2/3}sec^{-1/6}, $h_{corr}=52$ cm.

Results and Discussion

The reduction of Cd(II) in imidazole and tartrate media, separately, was found to be reversible and diffusion-controlled. The slopes of linear plots of $\log i/i_a - i$ vs $E_{d.e.}$ were of the order of 33 mV and the plots of i_d vs $h_{corr}^{1/2}$ were linear and passing through the origin.

Stability constants of simple complexes of Cd(II) with imidazole and tartrate: The stability constants of simple complexes of Cd(II) with imidazole and tartrate were determined separately prior to the study of mixed ligand system. Identical conditions were maintained in both the simple and mixed systems.

(i) **Cd(II)—Imidazole system:** A plot of $E_{1/2}$ vs $\log [\text{Im}]$ was a smooth curve thereby suggesting the formation of successive complexes. DeFord and Hume's method was applied to determine the stability constants of successive complexes. Four complexes, viz., [Cd(Im)]²⁺, [Cd(Im)₂]²⁺, [Cd(Im)₃]²⁺ and [Cd(Im)₄]²⁺ with stability constants, $\log \beta_{10}=2.7$, $\log \beta_{20}=4.0$, $\log \beta_{30}=5.3$ and $\log \beta_{40}=7.0$ are formed, $F_1[X]$ functions of simple complexes of Cd(II) with imidazole are presented in Table 1.

(ii) **Cd(II)—Tartrate system:** In this case the plot of $E_{1/2}$ vs $\log [\text{Tart}^{2-}]$ was straight line thereby showing the formation of a single complex. The

TABLE 1—VALUES OF $F_{ij}[X]$ FUNCTIONS FOR Cd-IMIDAZOLE SYSTEM

$[Cd^{2+}] = 1 \times 10^{-3} M$; $\mu = 2.0$ (NaNO₃); pH=8

[Im] M	$-E_{1/2}$ V vs (S.C.E.)	i_d div.	$F_{00}[X]$	$F_{10}[X]$ $\times 10^{-2}$	$F_{20}[X]$ $\times 10^{-3}$	$F_{30}[X]$ $\times 10^{-4}$	$F_{40}[X]$ $\times 10^{-5}$
0	0.605	113					
0.02	0.636	110	11.49	5.24			
0.04	0.660	110	74.61	18.40	38.50	5.87	
0.06	0.675	110	162.63	26.93	86.50	4.41	
0.08	0.690	108	787.04	98.25	116.56	18.32	14.15
0.10	0.698	106	1495.62	149.46	144.46	13.44	11.40
0.20	0.732	104	21561.50	1078.02	536.51	26.32	12.15
0.30	0.754	104	119718.00	3990.56	1328.52	43.95	13.96
0.40	0.762	104	223285.00	5582.35	1391.33	34.60	10.20
0.50	0.782	104	1060910.00	21218.18	4212.62	84.65	16.53
0.60	0.784	97	1829410.00	22156.80	3691.96	61.36	10.00

$\beta_{00}=1, \beta_{10}=5 \times 10^3, \beta_{20}=10 \times 10^3, \beta_{30}=2 \times 10^5, \beta_{40}=11 \times 10^5$

composition and the stability constants were determined by Lingane's method. This gave the composition of the complex species as $[Cd(Tart)_2]^{2-}$ with stability constant $\log \beta_{22} = 3.72$.

(iii) *Cd(II)—Imidazole-Tartrate-Mixed system*: Imidazole concentration was varied from 0.02M to 0.2 M and that of tartrate was kept constant at 0.1M. It was found that the $E_{1/2}$ values were greater as compared to those obtained in the absence of tartrate, thereby showing the formation of mixed complexes. The system was repeated at another concentration of tartrate (0.2M).

The method of Schaap and McMasters⁷ was used to determine the values of the stability constants of mixed complexes. The polarographic characteristics and $F_{ij}[X]$ functions of mixed complexes of Cd(II) with imidazole and tartrate, at fixed $[Tart]^{2-}$ (0.1M and 0.2M) have been presented in Tables 2 and 3.

The stability constants of the mixed complexes were calculated from the constants A, B, C, D and E. Four mixed complexes as noted below are formed:

TABLE 2—POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS AND $F_{ij}[X]$ FUNCTION OF Cd-IM-TART MIXED SYSTEM [TARTRATE] = 0.1M (FIXED); $\mu = 2.0M$ (NaNO₃); pH=8

[Im] M	$-E_{1/2}$ V vs (S.C.E.)	i_d div.	$F_{00}[X]$ $\times 10^{-1}$	$F_{10}[X]$ $\times 10^{-2}$	$F_{20}[X]$ $\times 10^{-3}$	$F_{30}[X]$ $\times 10^{-4}$	$F_{40}[X]$ $\times 10^{-5}$
0.00	0.605	112					
0.02	0.655	105	4.24				
0.04	0.673	104	21.58	4.13			
0.06	0.688	103	69.98	10.83	119.83	16.47	22.45
0.08	0.700	102	180.05	21.88	223.50	26.06	28.82
0.10	0.703	101	339.00	33.40	294.00	27.90	25.08
0.15	0.727	100	1505.80	100.00	640.00	42.40	26.26
0.20	0.733	99	2145.46	107.02	515.00	25.00	-

$A = 50, B = 4 \times 10^3, C = 15 \times 10^3, D = 8 \times 10^4, E = 25 \times 10^4$

TABLE 3—POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS AND $F_{ij}[X]$ FUNCTIONS OF Cd-IM-TART MIXED SYSTEM [TARTRATE] = 0.20M (FIXED); $\mu = 2.0M$ (NaNO₃); pH=8

[Im] M	$-E_{1/2}$ V vs (S.C.E.)	i_d div.	$F_{00}[X]$ $\times 10^{-2}$	$F_{10}[X]$ $\times 10^{-3}$	$F_{20}[X]$ $\times 10^{-4}$	$F_{30}[X]$ $\times 10^{-5}$	$F_{40}[X]$ $\times 10^{-6}$
0.00	0.605	112					
0.02	0.672	100	2.10				
0.04	0.688	99	7.92	13.31	13.29	23.20	48.03
0.06	0.698	98	16.03	23.38	25.60	36.07	53.46
0.08	0.708	97	35.31	41.63	42.04	47.56	54.45
0.10	0.717	96	71.94	69.94	61.94	57.90	53.94
0.15	0.737	95	345.35	223.91	147.27	95.51	61.00
0.20	0.750	94	961.16	380.50	150.25	73.12	-

$A = 200, B = 8 \times 10^3, C = 4 \times 10^4, D = 4 \times 10^5, E = 53 \times 10^5$

The mixing constant K_M (equilibrium constant) for the reaction:

indicates the relative stability of mixed complexes in solution as compared to the parent binary complexes. This is given by the following relation⁸⁻⁹

$$K_M = \beta_{11} / \sqrt{\beta_{20}\beta_{02}}$$

This comes out to be $\log K_M = 0.65$.

The positive value of log of mixing constants thus, shows that the mixed complex $[Cd(Im)(Tart)]$ is somewhat more stable than the simple bis complexes of Cd(II) with imidazole and tartrate i.e., $[Cd(Im)_2]^{2+}$ and $[Cd(Tart)_2]^{2-}$.

Cd(II) is hexacoordinated. Five mixed complexes existing in solution have the following equilibria (Table 4). The equilibrium constants (log values) have been calculated and written in front of each equilibrium.

TABLE 4—EQUILIBRIA INVOLVED IN FOUR MIXED COMPLEXES AND EQUILIBRIA CONSTANT (K) VALUES

Equilibrium	log K at 25°
1. $Cd^{2+} + Im + [Tart]^{2-} \rightleftharpoons [Cd(Im)(Tart)]$	4.52
2. $Cd^{2+} + Im + 2[Tart]^{2-} \rightleftharpoons [Cd(Im)(Tart)_2]^{2-}$	4.40
3. $Cd^{2+} + 2 Im + 2[Tart]^{2-} \rightleftharpoons [Cd(Im)_2(Tart)_2]^{2-}$	6.00
4. $Cd^{2+} + 3 Im + [Tart]^{2-} \rightleftharpoons [Cd(Im)_3(Tart)]$	6.00
5. $[Cd(Im)(Tart)] + 2 Im \rightleftharpoons [Cd(Im)_2(Tart)]$	1.48
6. $[Cd(Im)(Tart)_2]^{2-} + Im \rightleftharpoons [Cd(Im)_2(Tart)_2]^{2-}$	1.60
7. $[Cd(Im)(Tart)_2]^{2-} + 2 Im \rightleftharpoons [Cd(Im)_3(Tart)] + [Tart]^{2-}$	1.60
8. $[Cd(Im)_2]^{2+} + [Tart]^{2-} \rightleftharpoons [Cd(Im)(Tart)]$	1.82
9. $[Cd(Im)_2]^{2+} + 2[Tart]^{2-} \rightleftharpoons [Cd(Im)_2(Tart)_2]^{2-}$	2.0
10. $[Cd(Tart)_2]^{2-} + Im \rightleftharpoons [Cd(Im)(Tart)_2]^{2-}$	0.68
11. $[Cd(Tart)_2]^{2-} + 2 Im \rightleftharpoons [Cd(Im)_2(Tart)_2]^{2-}$	2.28
12. $[Cd(Tart)_2]^{2-} + 3 Im \rightleftharpoons [Cd(Im)_3(Tart)] + [Tart]^{2-}$	2.28
13. $[Cd(Im)_2(Tart)] + Im \rightleftharpoons [Cd(Im)_3]^{2+} + [Tart]^{2-}$	1.00

From the above equilibrium constant values the tendency of a ligand to add to a complex and to substitute another ligand may be compared. It is seen that 'Im' adds to $[Cd(Im)(Tart)_2]^{2-}$ complex readily. The saturated mixed complex $[Cd(Im)_3(Tart)]^{2-}$ can accommodate [Im] in place of

$[\text{Tart}]^{2-}$ i.e., Im can replace Tart^{2-} . The ligand Im has a tendency to replace Tart^{2-} from $[\text{Cd}(\text{Im})_2(\text{Tart})]$ mixed complex. Thus complexing tendency of Im is much more than Tart^{2-} . The same conclusion may be drawn from the substitution of Im in place of Tart^{2-} in complex $[\text{Cd}(\text{Tart})_2]^{2-}$. Equilibria 8,9 favour mixed complexation over the simple one.

The stability of four mixed complexes as seen from their overall stability constants follows the order :

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